

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were ... or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Identification of long-duration semidwarf rice cultivars for low-lying situations in different agroclimatic zones of West Bengal

P. Mukherjee and A. R. Debnath, Rice Research Station (RRS), Chinsurah, West Bengal, India

A multilocation investigation was conducted during the 1979 wet season to identify suitable rice cultivars for low-lands (20-50 cm water level) in specific agroclimatic zones in West Bengal. The entries were promising rice cultivars of diverse genetical constitution from coordinated trials, and mutant and hybrid derivatives developed at RRS, Chinsurah; the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack; other institutions of India and IRRI.

Sixteen promising long-duration (140 days or longer in the wet season) semidwarf rice cultivars were fitted in a

randomized block design with 3 replications. Plot size (net) was 4.6 × 2.7 m, with a spacing of 20 × 15 cm. Fertilizer was applied at a rate of 80 N:40 P₂O₅:40 K₂O kg/ha.

The table shows that at Chinsurah, grain yields ranged between 5 t/ha for CR1011 and 2.4 t/ha for CNM539. CR1006 (4.8 t/ha) and Pankaj (check) (4.7 t/ha) ranked 2d and 3d.

At Bankura, the grain yield was poor because of drought. Nevertheless, IR34 and IR4219-35-3-3 yielded nearly 3 t/ha and CR1002 and IET5638 yielded 2 t/ha. CO 40 was completely damaged.

The trial at Krishnanagar also suffered because of drought. Only IR4219-35-3-3 yielded 2.6 t/ha, and Pankaj (check) yielded only 1.9 t/ha.

On the basis of average grain yields at three sites, the cultivars IR4219-35-3-3, Pankaj, IR34, CR1002, and CR1006 are suitable for low-lying areas in different zones of West Bengal. ■

Mean yield of long-duration semidwarf rice cultivars in low-lying areas during 1979 wet season at 3 sites in West Bengal, India.

Cultivar	Growth duration (days)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
		Chinsurah	Rankura	Krishnanagar	Varietal mean
CR1002	142	4.4	2.0	1.4	2.6**
CR 1006	160	4.8*	0.8	1.7	2.6**
CR 1009	152	4.3	1.2	1.3	2.3
CR1010	156	4.5*	0.9	1.3	2.2
CR1011	151	5.0*	0.7	1.3	2.3
IET5638	145	4.4	2.0	0	2.1
IET5656	155	4.2	1.9	0.7	2.3
CO 38	143	3.6	1.9	0.8	2.1
CO 40	170	4.0	0	0.5	1.5
CN 195	143	3.7	1.4	0.6	1.9
CN643	150	3.7	1.2	0.8	1.9
CN644	154	3.5	1.3	0.5	1.8
CNM539	145	2.4	1.1	0.8	1.4
IR34	140	3.6	2.9*	1.6	2.7**
IR4219-35-3-3	150	4.0	2.9*	2.6*	3.2**
Pankaj (check)	145	4.7*	1.8	1.9	2.8**
L.S.D. (0.05)		0.5	0.6	0.4	

*Indicates at par. **Indicates recommended.

Delay in flowering of some lines during rapid generation advance

S. K. Bardhan Roy, B. S. Vergara, and G. Pateña, Plant Physiology Department, International Rice Research Institute

In the rapid generation advance (RGA) method the plants are subjected to short days and high temperature so they can be harvested 60-90 days after sowing. But we have noted that the flowering of

many plants in several crosses was delayed despite the short-day treatment. Some plants in crosses such as G. Benton 1101/IR42, DA29/IR42, and BR4/Patnai 23 matured as late as 134 days after sowing.

A study of the parents showed that crosses involving two parents of long basic vegetative phase (BVP) (such as G. Benton 1101/IR42 and DA29/IR42) resulted in delayed flowering of many lines (see table). But in crosses where one or both parents have short BVP, such as Silewah/Hokkai 241, the resulting progeny are early flowering.

The delay in flowering of certain crosses is mostly the result of long BVP. Thus, a line with a BVP of 60 days will take longer than 100 days to mature. Such crosses tend to diminish the advantage of RGA because the possibility of 3 generations/year becomes difficult.

The BVP, if known, should be consi-

Basic vegetative phase (BVP) and growth duration of varieties involved in crosses. IRRI, 1981.

	BVP	Growth duration (days)
G. Benton 1101	60	F ₂ = 122
IR42	49	F ₃ = 99
DA29	41	F ₂ = 113
IR42	49	F ₃ = 134
BR4	40	F ₂ = 115
Patnai 23	41	F ₃ = 106
Silewah	45	F ₂ = 82
Hokkai 241	13	F ₃ = 67
		F ₄ = 70
		F ₅ = 75
Silewah	45	F ₂ = 85
IR2793-80-1/ IR747B2-6-3	short	
Silewah	45	F ₂ = 103
IR52	medium	

dered in determining what crosses to run through RGA. Crosses with long BVP that are insensitive to photoperiod could be planted in the field because the growth duration in the RGA is not considerably shortened and, in some cases, is actually delayed. ■

Performance of IR36 in Karnataka, India

B. S. Naidu, M. Mahadevappa, S. S. Inamdar, K. Maharudrappa, and Jayaram, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

In Karnataka, about 55% of the rice area is planted to 16 recommended high yielding varieties. Some more area could be brought under high yielding rices by filling the extension gap. But special varieties with multiple resistance, interme-

diate plant stature, and earliness are needed for the area still planted to native rices.

Recent research and minikit results have indicated that IR36 has potential to supplement the currently recommended early-maturing, high-yielding varieties. IR36 has four attractive features: long slender grain, tolerance for salinity, tolerance for iron deficiency, and early maturity. This combination of characteristics cannot be found in any variety on the current recommended list.

Performance of IR36 in Karnataka, South India, 1978-80.

Year	Season	Variety ^a	Sites ^b (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over check varieties
1978	Wet	IR36	5	5.1	
		Rasi		4.7	9
		IR20		4.6	11
		Ratna		4.2	21
1978	Upland trial	IR36	1	4.8	
		Rasi		4.4	9
1979	Wet	IR36	3	4.4	—
		Mandya Vani		3.9	13
		IR20		4.4	—
		Pushpa		4.0	10
1980	Wet	IR36	1	4.1	
		Madhu		3.8	8
		Pushpa		3.3	24

^aSome check varieties were not included at all sites. ^bMandya, Mangalore, Mugad, Dhadesugur, Hebbal, Nagenahalli, and Ankoal, Karnataka, India.

Performance tests conducted at different sites and across seasons in the rice experiment stations of Karnataka show the superiority of IR36 over Rasi, Ratna, Mandya Vani, Madhu, IR20, and Pushpa (see table).

IR36 also was evaluated for two seasons through minikit trials in farmers' fields and will be tested for a third season. It is hoped that IR36 will supplement other early varieties in the districts of Bangalore, Tumkur, Kolar, Chitradurga, Bellary, Raichur, Shimoga, and Dharwad. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Aflatoxins in Sri Lankan rice

J. M. R. S. Bandara, plant pathologist; and H. A. Ratnasoma, Department of Agricultural Biology, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Peradeniya, Peradeniya, Sri Lanka

Carcinogenic aflatoxins are produced by the fungi *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus* that commonly grow on cereals and legumes in tropical climates. In Sri Lanka, rice is mainly consumed as raw *kekulu* processed (with or without bran) or parboiled rice (brown or polished). In parboiling, rough rice is soaked, steamed and sun-dried before milling. The chances of grains becoming moldy during this procedure are high. Various types of rice were examined for the relationship of processing method to aflatoxin contamination.

About 27% of the rough rice samples collected from Kandy were contami-

Occurrence of aflatoxin B₁ in Sri Lankan rice.

Rice	B ₁ (ppm)	Rice class
BG90-2	0	rough
BG94-1	0	rough
BG400-1	trace +	rough
BG379-2	0	rough
BG34-8	0.056	rough
MI39-193-1	0	rough
MI639-124-23	0	rough
MI290-32	0	rough
BW265	0.024	rough
BW272-6B	0	rough
BW272-8	0	rough
Parboiled samba	0	polished
Parboiled	0.128	polished
Parboiled	0.234	brown rice